

Perceived Impact of Conflict Management Strategies on Teachers' Job Satisfaction in Public Primary Schools of Gusau, Zamfara State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Background: This study examines the perceived impact of conflict management strategies on teachers' job satisfaction in public primary schools of Zamfara State, Nigeria. A null hypothesis was formulated to guide the study.

Methodology: The study adopted a correlational research design. The population of the study comprised all the 1,391 teachers serving in 152 public primary schools in Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State. The sample size of 255 teachers were selected as participants through Simple random sampling technique using Research Advisors (2006) table of determining sample size. A structured questionnaire titled 'School Conflict Management and Teachers' Job Satisfaction Questionnaire (SCMATJSQ)' was employed as the instrument for data collection. The data analysis was made using inferential statistics through Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient.

Findings/Results: Results from the study revealed that, there was a very significant relationship between school conflict management strategies and teachers' job satisfaction with statistical value of ($r = 0.982, p < 0.05$).

Implications: The result implies that effective conflict management strategies in schools have a strong positive influence on the job satisfaction of teachers.

Conclusion: Based on findings, the study concludes that the relationship between conflict management and job satisfaction is very significant, indicating that the way conflicts are managed in schools plays a critical role in teacher satisfaction.

Recommendations: The study therefore recommends that, the government, through the Local Government Education Authority (LGEA) and State Universal Basic Education Board (SUBEB), should organize conferences, workshops and seminars for the primary schools headteachers to have in-depth understanding of different conflict management strategies and the approaches to follow in adopting such strategies in their respective schools.

Keywords: Conflict, conflict management, teachers, job satisfaction

Introduction

Employees' job satisfaction is an essential concern in goal achievement in an organization, which leads to enhancing organization's productivity (Price, 2001). Job satisfaction among teachers has received immense importance in increasing the quality of education. Teachers' job satisfaction is essential for succeeding in qualitative education through effective involvement and true commitment to teaching (Rathnayake & Jagoda, 2023). However, conflict is an inevitable aspect of human interaction, particularly in educational institutions where diverse interests, goals, and personalities converge (Rahim, 2011).

Effective conflict management is crucial for fostering a positive working environment and enhancing job satisfaction among teachers (Omede & Oguche, 2020). Teachers who are satisfied with their jobs are happy, which often reflects their interactions with other teachers and students' satisfaction (Tillman & Tillman, 2008; Ronfeldt et al., 2013). Bahtilla and Hui (2021), proclaimed that, satisfied teachers are more likely to remain in the teaching profession, come to class regularly, while dissatisfied teachers are more likely to miss classes and look for other job opportunities.

Teachers' who are satisfied with their jobs show a higher level of commitment than those who are dissatisfied. In opposite viewpoint, teachers who are not satisfied with their careers can have a negative impact on students' learning and the overall performance of the schools. It is important to note that teachers' job satisfaction greatly influences their performance, which tends to influence students' academic performance (Bahtilla & Hui, 2021).

In Nigeria, education is divided into different levels. The levels are pre-primary, primary, secondary and tertiary levels. Primary education as stated in the National Policy on Education (2014) is the education given in institutions for pupils aged 6-12 years. The subsequent system of education is built upon primary-level education. Therefore, the key to the success or failure of the whole education system is dependent on what happens at this stage. In other words, it is the first formal foundation upon which all other formal levels of education are built. Primary education is the stage where a child's character is fashioned. The development of sound attitude, morals, and the ability to communicate effectively begins at this first formal stage of learning. Primary education is essentially the most important stage in the life of a child. This underscores the importance the government place on this level of education.

Problem Statement

School as an organization is set up to achieve particular objectives. It accommodates personnel from general background and environment working together as a team with an aim to produce a balanced person (students). School as an organisation of learning cannot be voided of conflict hence it accommodates people of different functions and working together as a team for a purpose of achieving educational goals. Teachers in primary schools of Zamfara State face various conflicts arising from administrative decisions, resource allocation, interpersonal relationships, and external community influences. The way these conflicts are managed significantly impacts their level of job satisfaction, motivation, and overall performance (Akomolafe & Ojo, 2019).

Primary school teachers in Zamfara State operate in an environment characterized by frequent conflicts arising from school environment safety, inadequate remuneration, leadership issues, and school-community relations (Yahaya & Bello, 2022). Several research investigations such as that of Adebayo (2020) and Oresajo (2015) upheld that poor conflict management often leads to dissatisfaction, demotivation, and decreased commitment among teachers, which in turn affects the quality of education delivery. emphasizes that unresolved conflicts can escalate, leading to a decline in organizational effectiveness.

Furthermore, Oresajo (2015) emphasized that unresolved conflicts can escalate, leading to a decline in organizational effectiveness. Given the educational challenges in Zamfara State, particularly in the wake of insecurity and resource constraints, understanding the relationship between conflict management strategies and teachers' satisfaction is essential for policy formulation and school administration (Usman, 2021).

Based on the existing literature reviewed, it was found that, there are many research works conducted on the assessment of conflict management in schools and teachers' job satisfaction, however, there are no sufficient research works conducted specifically focused on how conflict management strategies affect teachers' satisfaction. It is against this background, this study seeks to examine the perceived impact of conflict management strategies on teachers' satisfaction in primary schools of Zamfara State, with the aim of providing recommendations for enhancing a conducive working environment

Research Objectives

The main objective of this study is to examine the perceived impact of conflict management on teachers' job satisfaction in public primary schools of Zamfara State, Nigeria.

Research Hypothesis

This study guided by the following null hypothesis and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

H₀₁ There is no significant impact of conflict management strategies on teachers' job satisfaction in public primary schools of Zamfara State.

Review of Related Literature

The concept of conflict management has enjoyed lots of scholarly attention over the decades. Brown (2010) defines conflict as a form of interaction between parties with different understandings, perceptions, and preferences. The process begins when one party discovers that one or more problems are being hampered or blocked by the other (Sisk, 2015). Conflict is an integral part of the human experience and a natural and inevitable social phenomenon. Chinwokwu (2013) defines conflict as friction that can arise when two or more people interact. It is an inevitable and unavoidable part of the human experience, rooted in the contradictory activities of individuals and groups. The other side must be connected by some social bond. This determines the degree of conflict that exists in the relationship and thus the strength of the expression of the conflict (Ajudeonu, & Ossai, 2022).

Conflict management is essential for containing conflict. This includes developing effective strategies at the macro level to minimise conflict dysfunction, improve constructive functioning, increase learning efficiency, and increase the effectiveness of the school system (Rahim, 2002). Therefore, conflict management means maintaining the vitality, innovation, and creativity of the organisation by minimising conflicts within it. Achieving this always requires the use of good conflict management strategies. Gunuselli and Hacifaztioglu (2009) argued that conflict management involves diagnosing conflict and intervening through appropriate strategies to achieve organisational and personal goals.

In any organization, conflict is inevitable in a school of mixed personalities (Ajudeonu, & Ossai, 2022). Conflict is destructive when it interferes with the smooth running of the school, leading to breakdowns in ineffective communication, poor working relationships, tensions, fights, poor performance, and animosity between team members (Bano, Ashraf, & Zia 2013). Well-managed conflicts,

however, can have interests that contribute to the balance between solidarity and legitimate interests within the conflict group.

The ability to manage or resolve conflicts is essential for school leaders to keep their schools running smoothly. Obasan (2004) opined that conflict is part of organizational life and may occur within the individual, between individuals, between individual and the group that an individual belongs to, and between two or more groups. He emphasized that conflict is generally perceived as dysfunctional, it can be beneficial because it may occur in different perspectives.

According to Oresajo (2015), conflict may be interpersonal or intergroup. It is interpersonal when it occurs between a superior and his subordinates or between two individuals at the same level of organizational hierarchy. Intergroup conflicts occur between two different groups such as two trade unions, two departments or management and the line staff while making an attempt to implement the organisational policies and programmes. Chaudhary and Arora (2023) stated that conflict management is the ability of an organization to identify the sources of conflict and put strategic measures in place to minimize or control conflict. To Alper and Law (2000), conflict management involves acquiring skills related to conflict resolution, establishing structures of conflict models, and putting strategic measures as well as approaches in place.

There are various type of conflicts. literature review conducted for the purpose of this study, it was observed that there are many times of conflict in organisations. However, in the context of this study, the following types of conflict were considered:

Inter-personal Conflict

According to George and Jones (2006), inter-personal conflict is conflict between individual members of an organisation occurring because of differences in their goals and values. In the school system, inter-personal conflict occurs between teacher versus teacher and students versus students. A frequent cause of inter personal conflict in the school system is personality clash. When two teachers

distrust each other's motives, dislike one another or for some other reason cannot get along.

Intra-group Conflict

Intra-group conflict is conflict that arises within a group, team or department (Griffin and Moorhead, 2007).

Inter-organisational Conflict

According to Isabu (2017), conflict that arises between one organisation and another is called inter-organisational conflict. In the school system, this can be conflict between the school and the environment, between this school and some other governmental bodies in the community.

Conflict Management Strategies

Conflict management is the process of identifying and dealing with conflict constructively and productively. The ultimate goal is to minimise the negative effects of conflict while capitalising on its potential positive effects to enhance learning and innovation (Blitz et al., 2020). In an organisational setting, conflict management includes the use of strategies and techniques designed to prevent conflict escalation and resolve interpersonal or group disputes in a way that benefits all parties involved. The goal is to create an environment where conflict can be transformed into opportunities for improvement and development (Boin et al., 2020). Strategies to conflict management are a futuristic detailed approach that looks into achieving long term wins for the parties involved in conflict (Kalu & Queen, 2024). Strategies include negotiation, collective bargaining, mediation, third party intervention, brainstorming and communication (Valente & Lourenço, 2022).

Ezekiel and Abdulraheem (2022) defined strategies for conflict resolution as those methods or tactics that may be employed to avoid, manage, or end disputes. Any school should prioritize conflict management techniques since they enable the reduction or management of the negative impacts of disputes. Therefore, primary

school headteachers are open to using a variety of dispute-resolution techniques in their institutions (Ademola et al., 2023). There are many elements and approaches to conflict management strategies, however, the following are considered in the current study: mediation strategy, stakeholders involvement strategy, professional development and training strategy, documentation and monitoring strategy, counselling services strategy, and role clarification, as well as task reassignment strategy.

Concept of Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction is a combination of psychological, physiological, and environmental circumstances (Sen, 2008). Judge et al. (2012) pointed out three components of individuals' psychological responses toward their job such as cognitive (evaluative), affective (or emotional) and job satisfaction is a set of those psychological responses. Castillo & Cano (2004) examined that the work itself was the most important factor that influenced job satisfaction, with working conditions being the least important.

Teachers' job satisfaction is defined as a teacher's feelings and perceptions of happiness and contentment with teaching (Agyekum et al., 2013). Job satisfaction and motivation are interrelated even though they are different two concepts. The relationship between the two concepts of motivation and job satisfaction suggests that theories of motivation are also considered theories of job satisfaction (Ngimbudzi, 2009). Job satisfaction is appeared to be positively correlated with motivation i.e. an increase in motivation causes to increase in job satisfaction while a decrease in motivation causes to decrease in job satisfaction (Singh & Tiwari, 2011).

Furthermore, according to Zymbylas & Papanastaiou (2006), teachers' job satisfaction refers to the matters related to conditions like student achievement, decision-making ability, self-growth, and so on. They also state that societal relationships are important in job satisfaction; interactions with students, relationships with colleagues, and opportunities to contribute to the growth of individuals and the development of society are some factors that teachers always

emphasise for their own satisfaction (Zymbylas & Papanastaiou, 2006). Teachers' job satisfaction refers to the attitude and feelings they show while performing their responsibilities in an educational institution (Bhut, 2020).

It indicates they are actively participating in classroom instructional activities and other institutional tasks to be performed in better ways (Toropova, Myrberg & Johansson, 2021).

Methodology

Descriptive research design of correlational type was employed for the purpose of this research. It is correlational approach because it is aimed at finding out the relationship between the two variables of the research (i.e. conflict management and teachers' job satisfaction). According to Creswell (2014) correlational designs are procedures in quantitative research in which researchers' quantity the relationship between two or more variables and the use of the relationships to make predictions. Similarly, in this study, survey method would be used to collect the data. Survey is a comprehensive method of data generation ranging from physical computations and frequencies to judgments (DeVellis, 2013). Survey involves the use of questionnaires in gathering data from the respondents.

The target population for this study comprised all public primary school teachers in Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria. According to Universal Basic Education (2025) and Zamfara State Ministry of Education (2025) there are 1,191 teachers serving in 152 public primary schools in Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State.

The sample of 291 teachers were selected as participants using Research Advisors (2006) table of determining sample size. Simple random sampling technique is considered in this study. According to Acharya (2013), in this technique, every individual has an equal chance of being selected in the sample from the population. Simple random sampling makes sure that every person in a population has an equal probability of being chosen as a response (Noor et al., 2022).

The sample size of 291 teachers was determined using the Research Advisors' (2006) table for determining appropriate sample sizes for known populations. A multistage sampling technique was employed to ensure representativeness and reduce sampling bias. The following stages were applied:

Stage 1. Stratification: The 152 public primary schools in Gusau Local Government Area were first stratified based on existing educational districts or school clusters to reflect administrative or geographical divisions within the area.

Stage 2. Proportionate Sampling: Within each stratum, the number of teachers to be selected was proportionately allocated based on the total number of teachers in each stratum. This ensures that schools with more teachers contributed more participants to the sample than schools with fewer teachers.

Stage 3. Simple Random Sampling: After determining the proportion of the sample for each stratum, simple random sampling was used to select schools and teachers within each stratum. This was done using a ballot box method, where names or codes of teachers were drawn randomly to ensure each had an equal chance of being selected (Acharya, 2013; Noor et al., n.d.).

Stage 4. Accidental (Convenience) Sampling: Finally, the selected teachers were approached, and only those available and willing to participate at the time of data collection were included. This stage was adopted to ensure timely data gathering and to accommodate field logistics.

A structured questionnaire was employed for the data collection. The instrument consists three (3) sections, namely: Section A covers 3 items on demographic information of the respondents. Section B hath 25 self-developed items on conflict management strategies designed on 5-point Likerts' scale ranging: (1) Strongly Disagree, (2) Disagree, (3) Slightly Agree, (4) Agree, and (5) Strongly Agree by ticking the appropriate number at the end of each statement. While, Section C covers 20 items on teachers' job satisfaction adapted from Almutairi (2020) the section was developed on 5-point Likerts' scale ranging: Very High Extent (VHE) = 5, High Extent (HE) = 4, Moderate Extent (ME) = 3, Low Extent (LE) = 2, Very

Low Extent (VLE) = 1. The instrument therefore has a total number of 48 items. The reliability of the instrument was determined through the Cronbach Alpha technique of determining reliability, and a reliability index of 0.82 was obtained. This indicates that the instrument is reliable for data collection. The questionnaire instruments were distributed to the respondents with the help of trained research assistants who helped in the distribution and immediate collection of the questionnaires in order to avoid missing or misplacement of the responses by the respondents.

The data analysis was conducted using both descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics was employed in analyzing the demographic data of the respondents using Frequency Distribution (F) and Simple Percentage (%); while, Mean (M) and Standard Deviation (SD) were adopted in measuring the levels of the teachers' job satisfaction as well as perceived main causes of conflict in primary schools setting. Furthermore, inferential statistics was employed in analyzing the perceived impact of conflict management on teachers' job satisfaction using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC).

Results

Prior to the conduct of the data analysis, the researcher observed that, out of the total number of 291 administered, 255 were returned. This indicates that the return rate stands at 87.63%.

Descriptive Statistics of the Variables

Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics for the two major variables used in the study: School Conflict Management and Teachers' Job Satisfaction. These include the mean and standard deviation, which serve as a prerequisite to validate the correlation analysis.

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics of Study Variables

Variables	N	Mean	Standard Deviation
School Conflict Management	255	3.76	0.54
Teachers' Job Satisfaction	255	3.81	0.49

Source: Researcher's Field Survey, 2025

Table 1 revealed that School Conflict Management has a mean score of (M = 3.76, SD = 0.54), this indicates that, on average, respondents perceived school conflict management strategies as fairly effective or above moderate.

Similarly, Teachers' Job Satisfaction has a mean score of (M = 3.81, SD = 0.49), this suggests that teachers, on average, report a moderately high to high level of job satisfaction. The slightly lower standard deviation also implies a consistent perception among teachers regarding their job satisfaction levels.

Table 2. The Pearson Product Moment Correlation Analysis on the Relationship Between School Conflict Management and Teachers' Job Satisfaction

Variable	Conflict Management	Teachers' Job Satisfaction
School Conflict Management	1	0.982
Sig. (2-tailed)		0.05
N	255	255
Teachers' Job Satisfaction	0.982	1
Sig. (2-tailed)	0.05	
N	255	255

Source: Researcher's Field Survey, 2025. **Note:** Correlation is significant at $p < 0.05$ (2-tailed)

Based on the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient results obtained in the table 1 ($r = 0.982, p < 0.05$), it was revealed that there was a very significant relationship between School Conflict Management Strategies and Teachers' Job Satisfaction among the government-owned public primary schools of Zamfara State, Nigeria. On this ground, since the correlation was found to be significant, the null hypothesis formulated to guide the study which stated that there is significant relationship between school conflict management and teachers' job satisfaction is therefore rejected.

Discussions

The findings of this study is in harmony with that of Sumanasena and Nawastheen (2022) who found in their study that, school conflict management practices such as conflict prevention and conflict mediation instills motivation among the school employees have a significant impact on the level of teachers' job satisfaction. Onyema et al. (2023) proclaimed their study that conflict management strategies adopted by school administrators and other relevant authorities of educational management and administration such as dialogue, emergency, prevention, mediation, persuasion, participatory, and collaboration strategies have significant impact on intrinsic teachers' job satisfaction.

In addition, the findings of this study are in-line with that of Ishola et al. (2019) who observed in their study that conflict management techniques in Nigerian school system contributes to the enhance effective teaching and learning wherein teachers' job satisfaction has been regarded as one of the major contributing factors. Furthermore, Crawford (2017) upheld that teachers' job satisfaction is a fundamental state of condition where teachers feel safe, recognized, and valued by the school community. Job satisfaction among teachers is affected by numerous factors including the conflict management strategies.

Conclusion

This study examined the perceived impact of school conflict management strategies and teachers' job satisfaction. The major finding of this research

confirmed that, school conflict management strategies have a highly significant impact on teachers' job satisfaction. Thus, in order to enhance the extent of teachers' job satisfaction, primary schools' headteachers should adopt the use of effective conflict management strategies in the respective schools.

Recommendations

Based on findings, this study recommends that, in order to enhance teachers' job satisfaction and promote a peaceful school environment, the government, through the Local Government Education Authority (LGEA) and the State Universal Basic Education Board (SUBEB), should implement a continuous professional development programme focused on conflict management strategies for primary school headteachers. This should be done by organizing periodic, mandatory workshops and seminars that will expose headteachers to various conflict management styles, practical case studies, and collaborative problem-solving techniques. Delivering this training through interactive and context-specific approaches will equip school leaders with the skills needed to effectively address workplace conflicts, strengthen interpersonal relationships, and create supportive school climates. The outcome of this initiative will be improved teacher morale, increased job satisfaction, and enhanced school effectiveness through reduced incidences of unresolved conflicts.

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References

- Ademola, J. C., Ubala, C. M., & Abdullahi, I. M. (2023). Influence of school administrators' conflict resolution strategies on teachers' job satisfaction. *Journal of Pedagogy and Education Science (JPES)*, 2(2), 132-144. <https://doi.org/10.56741/jpes.v2i02.320>
- Agyekum, N. N. A., Suapim, R. H., & Peprah, S. O. (2013). Determinants of job satisfaction among Ghanaian teachers. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 4(3), 43-50.
- Ajudeonu, H. I., & Ossai, A. G. (2022). Conflict resolution strategies and effective management of public secondary schools in Delta State, Nigeria. *Pinisi Journal of Art, Humanity and Social Studies*, 2(3), 146-153.
- Alper, S. D., & Law, K. (2000). Conflict management, efficacy and performance in organizational teams. *Personnel Psychology*, 53, 625-642.
- Bano, H., Ashraf, S., & Zia, S. (2013). Conflict: Factors and resolution strategies adopted by administrators of schools for visually impaired students. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 4(4), 405-408.
- Bhat, I. A. (2020). An overview of the factors affecting teachers' job satisfaction. *AEGAEUM Journal*, 8(3), 912. <http://aegaeum.com/>
- Blitz, L., Yull, D., & Clauhs, M. (2020). Bringing sanctuary to school: Assessing school climate as a foundation for culturally responsive trauma-informed approaches for urban schools. *Urban Education*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0042085916651323>
- Boin, A., Lodge, M., & Luesink, M. (2020). Learning from the COVID-19 crisis: An initial analysis of national responses. *Policy Design and Practice*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/25741292.2020.1823670>
- Brown, M. (2010). A global study of pay preference and employee characteristics. *Compensation & Benefits Review*, 47(2), 60-70.
- Castillo, J., & Cano, J. (2004). Factors explaining job satisfaction among faculty. *Journal of Agricultural Education*, 45(3), 65-74.
- Chandrasekar, K. (2011). Workplace environment and its impact on organisational performance in public sector organisations. *International Journal of Enterprise Computing and Business Systems*, 1(1), 1-16.

- Chinwokwu, E. C. (2013). The challenges of conflict management in a democratic society: An overview of insecurity in Nigeria. *American International Journal of Social Sciences*, 2(3), 93-103.
- Crawford, D. (2017). *Teacher job satisfaction as related to student performance on state-mandated testing* (Unpublished doctoral dissertation). Lindenwood University.
- Ejuchegahi, A. E. (2023). The effect of leadership styles on teacher job satisfaction in Nigerian secondary schools. *International Research in Education*, 11(2). <https://doi.org/10.5296/ire.v11i2.21012>
- Ekwevugbe, A. O., & Efetobor, S. (2025). Working conditions as a correlate of teachers' job satisfaction in Delta State Nigeria. *Asian Research Journal of Arts & Social Sciences*, 23(3), 83-91. <https://doi.org/10.9734/arjass/2025/v23i3652>
- Ezekiel, A. O., & Abdulraheem, I. (2022). Traditional methods of conflict management and resolutions: The case of the Old Oyo Empire. *European Journal of Management and Marketing Studies*, 7(4), 126-139.
- George, J. M., & Jones, G. R. (2006). *Contemporary management* (4th ed.). McGraw-Hill/Irwin.
- Griffin, R. W., & Moorhead, G. (2007). *Organisational behaviour: Managing people and organisation* (8th ed.). Houghton Mifflin.
- Gunuselli, A. I., & Hacifaztioglu, O. (2009). Globalization and conflict management in schools. *Cypriot Journal of Educational Sciences*, 4(2), 183-198.
- Isabu, M. O. (2017). Causes and management of school-related conflict. *African Educational Research Journal*, 5(2), 148-151.
- Ishola, M. A., Suleiman, Y., & Musa, A. F. (2019). Conflict management techniques in Nigerian school system. *Amity Journal of Management*, 7(2), 15-22.
- Judge, T. A., Hulin, C. H., & Dalal, R. S. (2012). Job satisfaction and job affect. In S. W. J. Kozlowski (Ed.), *The Oxford handbook of industrial and organizational psychology* (Vol. 1, pp. 496-525). Oxford University Press.
- Kalu, L. A., & Queen, J. E. (2024). Conflict management strategies and organizational performance of oil and gas firms in Rivers State. *British Journal of Management and Marketing Studies*, 7(2), 192-201. <https://doi.org/10.52589/BJMMSA3PYACHI>

- Ngimbudzi, F. W. (2009). *Job satisfaction among secondary school teachers in Tanzania: The case of Njombe District* [Master's thesis, University of Jyväskylä]. <https://jyx.jyu.fi/handle/123456789/25482>
- Okorji, P., & Nzewi, F. E. (2023). Organizational culture in schools as correlates of teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Abia State. *International Journal of Advanced Academic Research*, 9(6). <https://www.ijaar.org/organizational-culture-in-schools-as-correlates-of-teachers-job-satisfaction-in-public-secondary-schools-in-abia-state/>
- Olaifa, A. S., Abisoye, F. M., Adeoye, M. A., Ajewole, I. P., & Olaifa, E. O. (2024). Workload as determinant of teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools. *Jurnal Pedagogi dan Pembelajaran*, 7(2). <https://doi.org/10.23887/jp2.v7i2.70465>
- Omede, J., & Oguche, P. (2020). Conflict management and teachers' performance in secondary schools. *Journal of Educational Leadership*, 5(1), 23-39.
- Onyema, P. C., Momodu, B. E., & Erundu, C. (2023). A survey of conflict management strategies used to tackle students' unrest in tertiary institutions in Delta State Nigeria. *Unizik Journal of Educational Research and Policy Studies*, 16(2), 160-170.
- Oresajo, N. O. (2015). Conflict management in school organisation in Nigeria. *International Journal of Development and Management Review*, 10, 166-175.
- Price, J. L. (2001). Reflections on the determinants of voluntary turnover. *International Journal of Manpower*, 22(7), 600-624.
- Rahim, M. (2002). Towards a theory of managing organizational conflict. *The International Journal of Conflict Management*, 13(3), 206-235.
- Ronfeldt, M., Loeb, S., & Wyckoff, J. (2013). How teacher turnover harms student achievement. *American Educational Research Journal*, 50(1), 4-36.
- Sen, K. (2008). Relationship between job satisfaction and job stress amongst teachers and managers. *Indian Journal of Industrial Relations*, 44(1), 14-23.
- Singh, S. K., & Tiwari, V. (2011). Relationship between motivation and job satisfaction of the white-collar employees: A case study. *Management Insight*, 7(2), 78-90.
- Sisk, H. L. II. (2015). *Management and organization*. South-Western Publishers.

- Sumanasena, M. L. H., & Nawastheen, F. M. (2022). Teacher job satisfaction: A review of the literature. *Muallim Journal of Social Science and Humanities*, 6(4), 1-12.
- Tillman, W. R., & Tillman, C. J. (2008). And you thought it was the apple: A study of job satisfaction among teachers. *Academy of Educational Leadership Journal*, 12(3), 1-19.
- Tiwari, A. K. (2019). A comparative study on organizational commitment among government and private school teachers. *International Journal of Management, Technology and Engineering*, 9(2), 2109-2121.
- Toropova, A., Myrberg, E., & Johansson, S. (2021). Teacher job satisfaction: The importance of school working conditions and teacher characteristics. *Educational Review*, 73(1), 71-97.
- Valente, S., & Lourenço, A. A. (2020). Conflict in the classroom: How teachers' emotional intelligence influences conflict management. *Frontiers in Education*, 5. <https://doi.org/10.3389/educ.2020.00005>
- Zembylas, M., & Papanastasiou, E. (2006). Sources of teacher job satisfaction and dissatisfaction in Cyprus. *Compare: A Journal of Comparative and International Education*, 36(2), 229-247. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03057920600741289>